

PARAMETRIC SENSITIVITY OF AN ADVANCED COMPOSITES BI-PHASE EXPLICIT FINITE ELEMENT SOLVER

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ABSTRACT: The effects of damage parameter variations in the explicit finite element Bi-phase composite material model were studied. The damage-time history responses of three elements, selected within a sample aerospace composite panel, under dynamic loading conditions were closely studied for fibre damage, matrix volumetric and deviatoric damages and total damage. Several of the damage parameters were found to be highly sensitive to the slightest parametric variation, imposing considerable deviations to the predicted dynamic responses of the structures under investigation. The paper continues with identifying such parameters and provides a tabulated damage sensitivity reference that enables effective application of the Bi-phase composite model in investigating real-life aerospace composite design problems.

KEYWORDS: impact, damage tolerance, advanced aerospace composite structures, dynamic response, explicit bi-phase solver

INTRODUCTION

The application of advanced composite structures has shown tremendous growth in the recent decades, particularly in the Aerospace Industry. Within this sector, meeting strict damage tolerance and crash-worthiness requirements for composite materials is vital. This includes the stringent certification requirements that avoid extensive loss of performance during foreign object strike incidents. Currently, damage tolerance of composite structures is determined through broad and costly test programs. The use of advanced simulation tools promises to reduce design and validation out-lays, while improving impact resistance and performance. This underlines the importance of studying the capabilities and precision of the explicit codes that can effectively reduce the cost of certification by accurately determining the behaviour of advanced composite structures under impact conditions.

Although the explicit codes provide an understanding of the fully non-linear behaviour of composite structures under impact, they are yet to be conclusively investigated to ensure the validity of their predictions. This paper, aims to comprehensively review one such numerical approach, the Bi-phase material model, integrated in an explicit finite element (FE) code, Pam-Shock/Crash [1]. The material model offers to effectively calculate the responses of advanced composite structures to the high and low velocity impact damage events. However, the level of accuracy of the responses predicted by this method is contingent to several defined Bi-phase parameters. This includes thirty damage parameters used to develop a comprehensive composite damage model for matrix/fibre tension, compression and shear failure interaction. Impacts can occur in composite aircraft components from a variety of accidental events such as dropped tools on the surface or in-service incidences such as hail or runway debris. This

material model has been used successfully by several researchers to simulate the behaviour of composite structures under impact, crash and crush conditions [2-5].

With over ninety simulation runs during this study, the effects of parameter variations, within the range of design allowables, used in aerospace applications, were investigated. This was done by considering a flat plate representative of a typical aerospace control surface. The Bi-phase parameters were analysed in two separate groups, elastic material properties and damage parameters. The sensitivity of the elastic parameters, including three-dimensional elastic and shear moduli and Poisson's ratios as well as tensile and compressive fibre elastic moduli, volume fraction and ply thickness have been reported by Bayandor et al. [6]. Among the elastic properties, Poisson's ration, ν_{12} , was found to be the least sensitive parameter, where the material model was proved to be highly sensitive to variations in "fibre volume fraction" and "fibre compressive and tensile elastic moduli", also discussed in Ref. 6.

FINITE ELEMENT METHODOLOGY

An FE impact model that represented a multi-layered aircraft composite panel was constructed in Pam-Shock. It is often the case to use one element analysis to investigate computer material models, where a sensitivity analysis is performed on a single element. This provides a clear understanding of the material under arbitrarily loads, however, is remiss in providing relevant information about the complex stress and damage regimes produced under actual impact events; hence consideration of using a large panel in this study.

The panel was a monolithic shell structure comprised of twelve plies, $[45/-45/0/90/45/-45]_s$. A hemispherical impactor was created using a rigid body with an internal velocity to impose the dynamic input onto the panel. The mesh density in the impact area was refined for the simulation to be able to more closely follow the progression of damage. Three elements, flagged in Fig. 1, were selected on the panel starting from the core of the impact area to consistently monitor the damage propagation along the specimen for all the simulation cases. Element 1052 was chosen under the impactor, Element 1281 was located far field (minimal damage) and Element 1165 was arbitrarily selected in the mid field (between Elements 1052 and 1281). The model had the following specifications:

- Panel plan size = 150 x 75 x 3 mm
- Impactor mass = 0.125 kg
- Energy of impact = 0.7 J

Fig. 1 The elements for which damage-time histories were recorded

The fibre, matrix volumetric and deviatoric, and total damages were determined using the Bi-phase material model. The basic Bi-phase model is a wide spectrum material solver customised to best analyse uni-directional continuous fibre reinforced composite structures [6]. The Bi-phase model considers orthotropic matrix for the composite resin phase while analysing the fibre phase as a one-dimensional medium. Stresses in each phase can independently propagate on the basis of the selected material laws

[3]. This means that the damage properties in the form of fibre breakage or resin cracks can grow and degrade separately. However, the overall element stiffnesses and strengths can be determined by superposition of the two independent phases. The theoretical modelling and assumptions made in establishing the mathematical relations are discussed in Refs 1 and 6. Fig. 2 shows the maximum nodal displacements resulted from the initial model response to the impact event.

Fig. 2 Maximum structural displacement in the reference run

The thirty Bi-phase composite damage parameters result from the fact that for each of the three types of damage, including fibre and matrix volumetric and shear damages, the Bi-phase model requires to be provided with five parameters. Each of these parameters needs to be defined for the simulated composite material used under both tension and compression.

The non-dimensionalised damage parameters investigated and their selected notations are as follows:

- a) Matrix shear damage properties (compressive and tensile):
 - compressive (tensile) matrix initial equivalent shear strain, $EpsiC$ ($EpsiT$)
 - matrix intermediate equivalent shear strain, $EpsIC$ ($EpsIT$)
 - matrix ultimate equivalent shear strain, $EpsuC$ ($EpsuT$)
 - matrix intermediate shear damage, $dsIC$ ($dsIT$)
 - matrix ultimate shear damage, $dsuC$ ($dsuT$)

- b) Matrix volumetric damage properties (compressive and tensile):
 - compressive (tensile) matrix initial volume strain, $EpsiVC$ ($EpsiVT$)
 - matrix intermediate volume strain, $EpsIVC$ ($EpsIVT$)
 - matrix ultimate volume strain, $EpsuVC$ ($EpsuVT$)
 - matrix intermediate volume damage, $dsIVC$ ($dsIVT$)
 - matrix ultimate volume damage, $dsuVC$ ($dsuVT$)

- c) Fibre damage properties (compressive and tensile):
 - compressive (tensile) fibre initial strain, $EpsiFC$ ($EpsiFT$)
 - fibre intermediate strain, $EpsIFC$ ($EpsIFT$)
 - fibre ultimate strain, $EpsuFC$ ($EpsuFT$)
 - fibre intermediate damage, $dsIFC$ ($dsIFT$)
 - fibre ultimate damage, $dsuFC$ ($dsuFT$)

To determine the required matrix damage parameters, according to Ref. 1, uni-axial compression and tension tests need to be conducted. The compressive and tensile stress-strain diagrams provide combinations of volumetric and deviatoric damages. Although deviatoric damage can be induced during both tension and compression tests, the volumetric damage is predominantly resulted during tension tests which can subsequently cause tensile volume stress with its associated disintegration growth and degradation. Compressive matrix volume strain does not appear to result in volumetric damage in most cases. Hence, the equivalent deviatoric damage behaviour can effectively be characterised from the compressive strain-stress diagrams. The properties of the fibre can also be determined through compression and tension tests conducted on isolated samples of the fibre.

Almost four-hundred damage-time histories were obtained through 10% variations imposed on the damage parameters of a Bi-phase composite material. To extract the large amount of data, several Pam-Shock post-processing command files were composed which considerably increased the efficiency of the required analysis by standardising and colour coding the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of this sensitivity analysis provided a comprehensive reference that can be used to understand important parameters in the Bi-phase material model.

A base-line analysis was performed as shown in Fig. 3. The four graphs shown represent aspects of the damage for the top ply only. In Fig. 3, $d(t,v)$ and $d(t,s)$ are the volumetric matrix and matrix shear damages, respectively. The fibre damage is represented by $d(f)$, where the total damage is approximately the sum of the three cases, denoted by $d(t)$.

Fig. 3 Initial response of the Bi-phase model response

To a degree the graphs are theoretical constructs of a complex mathematical procedure. From what was explained in the previous section however, the following are approximately true:

- Volumetric damage, $d(t,v) \approx$ Matrix normal damage.
- Deviatoric damage, $d(t,s) \approx$ Matrix shear damage.
- Fibre damage, $d(f) \approx$ Fibre damage.

- Total damage $d(t) \approx$ The sum of the above three damage cases.

The graph ordinate value of unity indicates that the ply in question has total failure, hence zero stiffness. A value less than unity indicates that the ply has sustained significant loss in stiffness due to damage. The abscissa axis is the time in *ms*.

The results indicated that the initial response of the first ply of the simulated composite structure to a 0.7 *J* impact event was: no fibre breakage, asymptotic shear damage response in Element 1 (1052), and complete volume failure in Element 1 (1052) and 0.52 *ms* delayed failure in Element 2 (1165) initiated at 0.4 *ms*. There was no significant fibre damage detected for this case. The damage propagation failed to reach Element 3 (1281). The total damage reflected the greatest damage values for each element.

In the following sections, the key sensitivities observed in the damage responses of the Bi-phase model to independent damage parameter variations are discussed. Negative and positive variations are considered concurrently.

Matrix Deviatoric Damage Properties

- *EpsiC (EpsiT)*: No major deviation from the reference run was detected.
- *EpsiC (EpsiT)*: An increase in the amount of fibre damage was evident. Shear damage followed a smoothed asymptotic failure in Element 1 (1052) with 0.04 *ms* delay, as shown in Fig. 4. The matrix volumetric performance of the structure appeared to have notably improved in the case of *EpsiT*.
- *EpsuC (EpsuT)*: The performance of the fibre phase in this case was reduced. Although matrix shear damage remained unaltered, it was apparent that, similar to the case of *EpsiT*, even the damage progression in Element 1 (1052), located directly under the impactor, was severely affected. This was in spite of the fact that in most cases, slight variation in the parameters did not influence the failure pattern at the centre of impact. As a result, the total damage was greatly affected (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4 Sensitivity of the damage response in the Bi-phase model to variations in *Epsi1*

Fig. 5 Sensitivity of the damage response in the Bi-phase model to variations in $Epsu$

- $dsIC$ ($dsIT$): As shown in Fig. 6, variations in this set of parameters predominantly affected the matrix volumetric impact damage tolerance.

Fig. 6 Sensitivity of the damage response in the Bi-phase model to variations in dsI

- $dsuC$ ($dsuT$): These two parameters largely influenced the total damage response of the simulated composite structure through imposing radical changes in the behaviours of the matrix volume.

Fig. 7 Sensitivity of the damage response in the Bi-phase model to variations in dsu

Matrix Volumetric Damage Properties

- $EpsiVC$ ($EpsiVT$): Sensitivity of the performance of the simulated model to variations in these parameters was minimal.
- $EpsIVC$ ($EpsIVT$): Tolerability of the fibre phase to the impact event remained almost unaffected. Nevertheless, according to Fig. 8, severe changes in the total and volumetric responses of the composite panel to the dynamic loading are noticeable.

Fig. 8 Sensitivity of the damage response in the Bi-phase model to variations in $Eps1V$

- $EpsuVC$ ($EpsuVT$): Both parameters, particularly the tensile matrix ultimate volume strain, constituted yet another critical parametric set important for the analysis of the uni-directional fibre reinforced composite structures using the Bi-phase model. While their influence on fibre damage and shear damage behaviours was minute, some major matrix volume and total damage progression trend changes were instigated (Fig. 9). Almost simultaneous failure of Element 1 (1052) in this figure is distinctive.

Fig. 9 Sensitivity of the damage response in the Bi-phase model to variations in $EpsuV$
(The black dotted line represents the initial response of the Bi-phase model.)

- $ds1VC$ ($ds1VT$): The effects of variations in these parameters on the damage responses are marginal.
- $dsuVC$ ($dsuVT$): In this case, considerable changes in how element failure occurred were detectable. Figs 10a and 10b underline the changes in the patterns of fibre, matrix volume and total damage progressions. Rather delayed volumetric failure of Element 1 (1052) and added damage tolerability of Element 2 (1165), leading to an asymptotic total failure of the element, are noteworthy.

Fig. 10a Sensitivity of the damage response in the Bi-phase model to variations in $dsuV$

Figure 10b Sensitivity of the damage response in the Bi-phase model to variations in $dsuV$

Fibre Damage Properties

- *EpsiFC (EpsiFT)*: Except for a sensitivity shown by the fibre damage response, the Bi-phase data did not show any particular dependency to the variations in initial values of these parameters.
- *EpsiIFC (EpsiIFT)*: Since in the Bi-phase model the fibre phase is analysed independently, variations in fibre intermediate strain, similar to the previous case, did not directly affect the damage output. Fibre damage behaviour however resembled that of the *EpsiF*.
- *EpsuFC (EpsuFT)*: Due to the fact that the energy of impact, applied as a boundary condition to the simulation model, can not cause fibre breakage, the response of the simulation to variations in fibre ultimate strain remained unchanged.
- *dsIFC (dsIFT)*: Again, since the boundary conditions can not initiate major fibre damage in the model, variations of these parameters did not influence the response of the simulation run.
- *dsuFC (dsuFT)*: The same argument, as that of *dsIF*, was valid for this case.

Summary of Results

Overall sensitivities of the Bi-phase material model to variations in the damage material properties are summarised in Table 1. For users of the Bi-phase material model, these results provide an indication of which of the 30 damage parameters must be determined with most accuracy.

CONCLUSION

A sensitivity analysis of the explicit FE Bi-phase composites model was performed. Combinations of over 356 data graphs were considered in order to capture deviations in the complex responses of the Bi-phase model to variations in its defining damage parameters. The damage parameters consisted of compressive and tensile fibre and matrix properties. Matrix shear and volumetric damage parameters constituted the matrix properties, each comprising of initial, intermediate and ultimate strains and intermediate and ultimate damage parameters. Fibre compressive and tensile properties also included five damage law parameters encompassing initial, intermediate and ultimate strains and intermediate and ultimate damage factors.

The analysis data, on a case-by-case basis, provided a clearer understanding of the Bi-phase material model response to parametric changes in the input damage variables. A summary of the results was reported that underlined the important sensitivities of the model.

The information gained can directly contribute to validating future explicit Bi-phase analyses for the purpose of design and certification of advanced composites used in numerous aerospace applications. Furthermore, the outcomes of this study can significantly help reduce the number of required physical tests and their associating costs conducted to verify the predicted numerical composite impact simulations. This will result in improved design and impact damage tolerance of future aerospace structures, and sharp reduction in the time and cost precincts of their development and certification phases.

Table 1 Effects of variations in damage parameters in the response of the explicit Bi-phase model

Parameters	Total Damage	Matrix Volumetric Damage	Matrix Shear Damage	Fibre Damage
Matrix Shear Damage				
<i>Epsi</i>	negligible	negligible	negligible	negligible
<i>EpsI</i>	weak	moderate	moderate	moderate
<i>Epsu</i>	weak	negligible	moderate	moderate
<i>dsI</i>	weak	negligible	moderate	moderate
<i>dsu</i>	weak	negligible	moderate	moderate
Matrix Volume Damage				
<i>EpsiV</i>	negligible	negligible	negligible	negligible
<i>EpsIV</i>	negligible	negligible	strong	strong
<i>EpsuV</i>	weak	negligible	strong	strong
<i>dsIV</i>	negligible	negligible	weak	weak
<i>dsuV</i>	weak	negligible	strong	strong
Fibre Damage				
<i>EpsiF</i>	moderate	negligible	weak	weak
<i>EpsIF</i>	moderate	negligible	weak	weak
<i>EpsuF*</i>	negligible	negligible	negligible	negligible
<i>dsIF*</i>	negligible	negligible	negligible	negligible
<i>dsuF*</i>	negligible	negligible	negligible	negligible

*Sensitivities have been substantiated in the absence of any fibre damage.

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